

23

Fig. S1 The particle size distributions of OPC, SL and SF.

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(a) SF

(b) SL

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Fig. S2 Microscopic morphology of (a) SF and (b) SL.

26

(a) SF

(b) SL

Fig. S3 XRD patterns of (a) SF and (b) SL.

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28 **SM.2 Corrosion depth**

29 The measurement procedure for the phenolphthalein-indicated low-alkalinity depth is shown
30 in Fig. S4. A phenolphthalein indicator solution (1 g phenolphthalein dissolved in 70 mL
31 ethanol and mixed with 100 mL distilled water) was sprayed onto the split surface to distinguish
32 the corroded and uncorroded regions. After the color development became stable, the corrosion
33 depth was observed using an OLYMPUS SZX10 stereoscopic optical microscope (**Fig. S4 (a)**).
34 In this study, the corrosion depth refers to the phenolphthalein-indicated depth of the low-
35 alkalinity region induced by carbonic acid water exposure. Given the non-uniformity of the
36 specimen surface, corrosion depth was measured at six different points, and the average value
37 was used to represent the corrosion depth at each corrosion age. A schematic illustration of the
38 measurement is provided in **Fig. S4 (b)**.

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(a) Optical microscope

(b) Measured depth

Fig.S4 Schematic diagram of corrosion depth measurement using an optical microscope.

SM.3 XRD

Fig S5. Depth-resolved XRD patterns of paste specimens after 180 days of immersion in carbonic acid water.

(c) SL30

(d) SFS15

Fig. S6. Depth-dependent fractions of CaCO_3 polymorphs in different binder systems after exposure to carbonic acid water.

SM.4 FTIR

Fig. S7. Deconvolution of the overlapping FTIR curves between 800~1200cm⁻¹

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41 **SM.5 SEM**

Fig. S8. The micro morphology in deterioration layer

Fig. S9. The micro morphology in carbonation layer

(a) Aragonite-type calcium carbonate

(b) Calcite-type calcium carbonate developed from vaterite

(c) Decalcified calcium carbonate affected by dissolution

Fig. S10. The micro morphology of corrosion product CaCO₃